

GUIDELINES TO AUTHORS

SUBMISSION OF MANUSCRIPTS

The manuscript of the article should be submitted to the office of the Research Management Cell (RMC), Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta, in electronic form through the email address: rupantaran.dmc@gmail.com. The manuscripts must be submitted within the submission deadline, which is notified by RMC. The submission notice can also be obtained from the official website of the campus: www.dmcampus.edu.np

AUTHOR GUIDELINES

The articles for submission must contain a sequence of **Title, Author information, Abstract, Keywords, Body** (introduction, methods and materials, results and discussion, and conclusion), and **References**. The articles should be a Microsoft word document within the limitation of 3000-5000 words including references in A4 size paper in **Times New Roman** or **Preeti** font. The whole document except the title should be in 12 point font if it is in Times new Roman, and 14 point if it is in Preeti. The authors are required to follow **APA style (seventh edition)** in Levelling of headings, Paragraph indentation, Tables and Figures, and in Citation and Referencing. There should be before zero after zero paragraph spacing, and 1 point line spacing in the body of the article. Authors are requested to consider following further guidelines.

Title: The title should be short as far as practicable, and it needs to reflect the main issue/s of the manuscript. It should be bold in 14 point font in Times New Roman, or 16 point in Preeti.

Author information: Below the title, the name of the author and email address must be flushed right. Other information such as the designation and workplace of the author/s should be given in the footnote.

Abstract: Abstract should be the gist of the whole article summarizing the context, purpose/s, methods, findings, conclusion and its contribution to knowledge. It should be in italic style within 150 to 250 words.

Keywords: There should be 4-6 keywords (in alphabetical order) chosen to capture the essence of the paper.

Manuscript body: Body is the main part of the manuscript that contains a sequence of IMRAD (INTRODUCTION, METHODS AND MATERIALS, and RESULTS AND DISCUSSION), and the CONCLUSION as the main components, which all are the level one headings. Under each of these main components, the manuscript can have other relevant sub-headings. For example, the Introduction may include objective/s, problem statement, and literature review. Likewise, the methods and materials may include the field of study, population, sample, source of data collection, research tools, and so on.

Tables and Figures: The Table/s should be concise and self-explanatory so as to permit readers to understand them without reference to the text. Each table should be numbered consecutively, the table number should be bold, and the title should be in non-bold italic font, e. g. **Table 1:** *Sentence structures and their communicative functions*. Table number and title should be placed at the top of the body of the Table. Similarly, each figure should have its consecutive number, the figure number should be bold, and the caption should be placed above the body of the Figure, e. g. **Figure 1:** *Availability of ICTs in the school*.

References: All the citations in the body of the manuscript should be presented as a list of references. The list of references should be placed at the end of the body of the article in alphabetical order, and emphasis should be placed on more recent publications. It is the responsibility of the author(s) to verify the accuracy of all references.